

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Bismuth with Tetrabutylammonium Perchlorate

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A number of quaternary ammonium salts find application as reagents in the determination of metal ions in micro-quantities¹. Here we report the use of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate for determination of bismuth in micro amounts. By using tetrabutylammonium perchlorate, the selectivity and sensitivity of the well-known iodide method for determination of bismuth is vastly improved.

Results and Discussion

When an ethanolic solution of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate is added to an acidic solution containing bismuth and potassium iodide, it forms an orange-yellow complex, which is extractable into chloroform. The extract absorbs maximum at 492 nm and obeys Beer's law for 2.5–25 ppm of bismuth. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be $1.07 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.019 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of bismuth respectively. The reagent blank has no absorption at 492 nm. It is found that when the acidity of the bismuth solution is 0.2–3 N with respect to sulphuric acid, 2 ml of 2% potassium iodide and 2 ml of 0.25% tetrabutylammonium perchlorate solution are sufficient to extract 2.5–25 ppm of bismuth by a single extraction with 10 ml chloroform. The optimum concentration of potassium iodide in the aqueous phase was maintained at 1–3% and that of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate 0.02–1%. A concentration of potassium iodide above 3% and that of acidity of aqueous phase above 3 N result in the high absorbance values due to liberation of iodine. Similarly, use of more than 1% tetrabutylammonium perchlorate creates difficulty in extraction due to the formation of emulsion. Of the various solvents like benzene, carbontetrachloride, n-butanol, isobutanol, isobutylmethyl ketone, chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane, ethylacetate tried, chloroform was found to be the most satisfactory for extraction of the complex. The colour and absorbance value of the complex remain stable for about 2 h in the solvent chloroform.

The effect of different foreign ions in the determination of bismuth (100 μg) was studied and the tolerance limit to cause an error < 3% in the recovery of bismuth was evaluated. It was found that Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ag^{I} , Au^{III} , Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , As^{III} , Sb^{III} , Pb^{II} , Sn^{II} , V^{V} , U^{VI} , Mo^{VI} , F^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CNS^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, CH_3COO^- , EDTA, citrate, thiourea and tartrate, when present in five-fold excess of bismuth did not interfere. However, equal amounts

of Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} and Cr^{VI} interfered seriously. Interferences due to Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} could be improved upto five-fold excess using thiourea as a masking agent.

Application : The present method was applied to determine bismuth from standard sample and a number of synthetic mixtures. The recovery of bismuth from lead concentrate, 42G (BAS Ltd. London) by the present method was excellent (error within 2%). Disolution of the sample was done following the standard method². Table 1 shows the recovery of bismuth from a number of synthetic mixtures. A sample containing 100 μg of bismuth was estimated ten times by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.5128 with standard deviation of ± 0.0019 absorbance unit and coefficient of variation of $\pm 0.38\%$.

Thus the proposed method is simple and selective, rapid and sensitive and compares well with many standard methods of determination of bismuth³.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF BISMUTH (100 μg) IN VARIOUS MIXTURES[†]

Amount of Bi = 100 μg	Mixture	Bi ^{II} found* ¹ μg
Sl. no.		
1.	$\text{Bi}^{\text{III}} + \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} + \text{Sn}^{\text{II}}$	101.80
2.	$\text{Bi}^{\text{II}} + \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} + \text{Au}^{\text{III}}$	99.80
3.	$\text{Bi}^{\text{III}} + \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} + \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$	98.80
4.	$\text{Bi}^{\text{II}} + \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} + \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$	98.00

*To which 500 μg each of ion added (in case of Pd, 60 μg added).

**Average of 3 determinations.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer with a pair of matched 1 cm glass cells was used. All chemicals and solvents were of A.R. quality.

A stock solution of bismuth(III) oxide (containing 1000 μg of bismuth per ml) was prepared in 2 N H_2SO_4 and solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by dilution with 0.1 N H_2SO_4 . A 0.25% solution of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate in ethanol and a 2% solution of KI in distilled water were prepared. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from chloride, nitrate or sulphate (in case of cations) and sodium, potassium or ammonium (in case of anions) salts.

Procedure : To an aliquot of bismuth solution containing 25–250 μg (made upto 10 ml with 0.1 N H_2SO_4) were

NOTE

added 2 ml each of KI solution (2%), tetrabutylammonium perchlorate solution (0.25%) and chloroform (10 ml). The resulting mixture was shaken for ~3 min and the orange-yellow organic layer was separated. To this organic layer, a small amount of anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was added to remove any retained water and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 492 nm against pure solvent. A calibration curve was prepared using identical procedure and the amount of bismuth present in unknown solutions was computed. To test interferences, the respective foreign ions were

added to the solutions of bismuth before addition of other reagents.

References

1. J. YOSHIMURA and K. UNEO, *Mem. Fac. Sci. Kyshu Univ. Ser. C. Chem.*, 1962, 4, 63 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 56, 2870); D. E. RYAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1956, 34, 1683; K. C. BAYAN and H. K. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, 53, 312, 915.
2. K. C. BAYAN and H. K. DAS, *Talanta*, 1988, 35, 57.
3. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals". 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 330.

